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A Narrative Understanding of Boundary Crossing by Vocational Teachers in their Career Path

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Abstract

The article explains the career path of vocational teachers. Vocational teachers, with few exceptions, have a background related to a different economic sector. The decision to become a teacher is challenging as it involves adapting to new behaviours, culture and regulations. Within the transformation process, an individual can cross the border from his/her initial occupational field to the vocational school. As a vocational teacher, the individual has to adapt several structural changes, pedagogical demands and trend in a vocational field. Drawing on the analysis of narrative interviews with 21 Estonian vocational teachers, the article highlights the factors and motives for becoming a vocational teacher and analyses the transition processes and perspectives of the vocational teachers' career. The individuals' career path has been analysed using the concept of boundary crossing. As the narrated career paths represents the individual's own view of career related factors, the career is considered a subjective career.

Keywords

boundary crossing, vocational teacher, professional understanding

1 Introduction

The recommendation that VET teachers should have sector-specific work experience has prompted VET schools to adopt strategies to attract industry professionals to become VET teachers (OECD, 2021). The fact that VET teachers mostly have occupational backgrounds is recognised (Andersson and Köpsén, 2015) but questions about motives of career change and the process of transformation need clarification.

It is recognised, that VET teachers regularly come to the occupation by “accident”, without a well-developed intention (Berger and D’Ascoli, 2012). Oftentimes, the career change from industrial worker to VET teacher takes place after the long career path, which may encompass periods of unemployment and employment in various organisations (Loogma, 2018). However, becoming a VET teacher is not the initial career plan but it rather seen as a condition in the choice when this becomes an alternative (Berger and Girardet, 2015). The recommendation that VET teachers should have sector-specific work experience (OECD, 2021) and usually have first work experience as specialist in an occupational field means that tend to be more committed to their initial (occupational) field and community. This can be explained by shorter

teaching experience and longer work-life experience outside school (ibid, p.340) Andersson and Köpsén (2015, p.340). During the transition to a VET teacher's position should to detach themselves from the world with which they once identified (Sarastuen, 2020, 346) and gain new identities, which at its best, includes both teacher identity and vocational identity (Fejes and Köpsén, 2014).

Nevertheless, before they can move between practical field and pedagogical field they have to cross the boundary from the vocational field to teaching.

2 The context of Estonian VET teachers' career

During the last 30 years, Estonian VET has undergone two main transformations. First, the transformation from Soviet system to a school-based system caused by the collapse of the Soviet planned economic system. The second wave of changes, which brought about structural changes, and therefore potentially influenced the careers of VET teachers, is related to the neoliberal turn and Europeanization in vocational education (Loogma, 2016). For VET teachers, however, it caused discontinuities as well as new starts (Loogma, 2018).

By the year 2009, several flexible new forms of vocational training, including targeting vulnerable groups (students without basic education, students with special needs) were ratified (Loogma, 2016). Almost simultaneously, the approaches of learner-centred and outcomes-based teaching were introduced.

In Estonian VET the term 'teacher' is used for both roles - teacher and trainer (Vocational Education Institutions Act, 2013), which means that teacher is expected to teach theoretical knowledge and practical skills.

The career of VET teachers is largely determined by the formal requirements, which have been laid out in the professional standards on the levels of the European Qualification Framework (EQF 5, 6, 7).

Most senior vocational teachers have experienced several career changes and their professional understanding has been formed in different working conditions, including aforementioned societal transition period, which meant the loss of work often requiring them to move into different economic sectors or occupational field. (Loogma, 2016).

The focus of this article is to highlight the motives and the transition processes of becoming a vocational teacher. For that, we examine the personal stories of vocational teachers.

We assume that both the structural circumstances, as well personal life-related circumstances are forcing career changes upon VET teachers and boundary-crossing activities.

3 Theoretical framework

The conceptual framework applied in this article comprises the concepts of career, subjective career, boundaries and boundary crossing processes in the career path.

The notion of a career means a process – a sequence of work-related experiences (Hall, 2002, 11) or a sequence of social positions filled by a person through their life or an aspect of their life such as their involvement in work' (Watson, 2017; 391). The notion of a subjective career refers to the distinction made between objective and subjective aspects of the career. While objective aspects of a career comprise the obvious movements between educational and work institutions, a subjective career is an individual's view on her/his career involving subjective experience and memories (Watson, 1980, 124; Young and Collin, 2000). The subjective career as a personal view of her/his career path enables to an individual critically reflect on the past changes and attribute meaning and consistency to her/his working life (Riverin-Simard, 2000; Hall and Mirvis, 2013).

However, the construction and shaping of the career are seen as an interplay between structural factors, particularly available opportunity structures (Watson, 2017) from one side

and self from another side (Young and Collin, 2000; Wolf, 2018; De Vos Van der Heijden and Akkermans, 2020).

Besides voluntary boundary crossing in their career path, some people are involuntarily pushed into a boundaryless career by structural changes (Guan et al., 2018). The notion of sustainable careers contributes to the prevailing sustainability debate and paying attention to the fit between an individual and her/his career, such as satisfaction and feeling of success, people's physical and mental health and well-being and economic revenue (De Vos, Heijden and Akkermans, 2020, 3).

The subjective career manifests itself in narratives about what and how individuals recall and relate to their life and career. In their memories and perceptions about their career, individuals try to attribute meaning and achieve coherence between various aspects of their working lives (Watson, 1980; Young and Collin, 2000).

The distinctions between professions or vocations, scientific fields and knowledge areas can be described and manifested using the concept of boundaries (Lamont and Molnar, 2002). Boundaries can be defined as social and cultural differences that give rise to discontinuities in interaction and action, simultaneously suggesting a sameness and continuity in the sense that within discontinuity two or more sites are relevant to one another in a particular way (Lamont and Molnar, 2002; Akkerman and Bakker, 2011, 140).

However, boundaries are not only barriers to continuity, as these embody the potential and resources for learning and innovation (Akkerman and van Eijck, 2013).

The movements between various sites of activities involve boundaries and boundary processes related also to horizontal learning in terms of new understandings and identity development, changed practices, and institutional development (Akkerman and Bakker, 2011, 142). In this article, we consider a career as a subjective career based on the memories and subjective understanding of the work-related contexts, motives of choices and movements.

4 Research questions

This paper will seek to answer the following research questions:

1. What kinds of motives and contextual factors, both structural and personal factors have impact on the career turns in the way of becoming a vocational teacher?
2. How is boundary crossing manifested in the course of becoming a vocational teacher?

5 Methodology

The research is based on narrative life history interviews, conducted with 21 vocational teachers. By nature, a narrative is a story of transformation, as while narrating about life the individual connects the past and the present, self and others (Lawler, 2002). We considered the narrative approach for achieving a better understanding of the career of vocational teachers that captures the experiences, events and “contextual influences in a way that other research methods may not’ (Bold, 2012, 21).

The construction of the sample was based on the principle of heterogeneity. A total of 8 interviewees were female, and 13 were male, most (17) were older than 45. They had worked as welders, chefs, mechanics, secretaries, builders, engineers, tractor drivers or service workers. Half of the participants had higher professional education before and some had acquired pedagogical higher education after becoming a VET teacher.

The two-step narrative interview method was applied. First, in the non-structured interview stage, the interviewee talked about the way they have got to the position of a vocational teacher. In the second stage, the questions, specifying the necessary aspects of the life stories, work identity and future perspectives were discussed.

In analysing the interviews, we applied the thematic analysis approach (Braun and Clarke, 2006). Analysis started with open coding. Although we implemented mainly an inductive approach, the theoretical concepts were used in identifying the content units. Then we aggregated the content units into categories and finally, integrated the categories into themes and selected illustrative quotes.

6 Findings

From the narratives collected from the participating vocational teachers, we distinguished the following themes: 1) becoming a vocational teacher; 2) VET work and boundary crossing; 3) VET teachers' role and position, and 4) future perspectives, which revealed factors such as career satisfaction, success in boundary crossing, and the vocational allegiance.

Becoming a vocational teacher

Becoming a vocational teacher was unplanned. The interviewees became vocational teachers based on a former professional career or their educational path and mostly (13) after an offer from the VET school. Motives of younger vocational teachers included the prospects for self-development, better job security compared to the private sector, potential training programmes, and an intriguing challenge. For instance, Marko accepted the VET school proposal at the age of 23.

I was wondering why to go ... I will just get professional training through school more than in a private company. (Marko, 30)

For some, becoming a vocational teacher was due to the lack of suitable options in the region, that it provided a steady salary, and the need to leave unemployment.

I had been unemployed for a whole year. ..., I applied everywhere of course, wherever I could ... Then it happened that I was invited to a job interview and they asked if I wanted to apply my knowledge in teaching (Priit, 53)

Becoming a vocational teacher was tied up with changes in their personal life, such as divorce. For example, after his divorce, Arno re-evaluated his previous career.

And money didn't taste good anymore, and well, I was its slave, but I also lost my life to it. (Arno, 58)

Some who recognised the teaching profession as an adolescent showed personal initiative. In some cases, the decision to become a vocational teacher was made after acknowledging lack of satisfaction in their current work.

I stepped inside the door and asked whether you need a good 50-year old, And they said, of course, they welcomed me with open arms. (Riina, 50)

Some interviewees exercised agency when responding to job advertisements.

To conclude, becoming a vocational teacher was mostly an unplanned decision. Three patterns can be distinguished when it comes to becoming a vocational teacher: 1) the invitation to teach came from vocational schools; 2) vocational teachers exercised agency by replying to an advertisement or enquiring at the vocational schools about job opportunities or 3) vocational teachers left teaching but returned.

Vocational teachers work as boundary crossing

Becoming a vocational teacher brought about substantial changes. Difficulties in adjusting to the new field of practice were more often linked to the absence of learning materials and students not meeting their expectations. These aspects were reinforced by the fact that vocational teachers often lacked pedagogical training. Sometimes, adjusting to the requirements of the new or different socio-cultural environment of a vocational school in terms of self-control, use of language, dress code and other aspects took several years.

And of course, if you go there from construction sites, then you kind of speak in slang, you are not that type who chooses his or her words, as is expected from teachers ... and I remember that there were people who kicked me under the table – because ...my vocabulary, of course, started to change slowly towards more politeness (Ene, 64)

Some VET teachers, getting out of unemployment, perceived this career development as a step backwards. Priit, despite his initial disappointments and acclimatisation, found meaningful perspectives in the work of vocational teachers, and started to learn to manage his classes better.

Absolutely, the only reason I'm at university today ... I just have to do it, for this simple reason that, first of all, I could deal better with my romps [students]. This is ... the most important. (Priit, 53)

The transformation period from a specialist to a vocational teacher, marked by changes in professional identity, varied greatly. Some teachers considered themselves vocational teachers after a few years, but some maintained a stronger relation with their initial occupational field, considering themselves primarily as a specialist in a vocational field. However, teachers who remarked on the lack of collegial support and participation in teacher networks tended to remain identified with their previous field rather than with the teaching profession. For example, Raivo, who has worked as a vocational teacher for more than ten years, defines himself on the basis of his former occupation. Raivo feels isolated and has no interest in pedagogical courses.

I still feel like a lifelong electrician and want to teach what electricians need to know. (Raivo, 64)

At the beginning of his vocational teacher's career, Raivo was in his 50s. According to Raivo's narration he does not remember any support from the VET school. Some of those who started working as VET teachers at a younger age recognised that they had a mentor.

Riina experienced the process of becoming VET teacher rather as cultural border crossing resulting in the changing manner of speech, wardrobe, and behaviour. She passed pedagogical courses and created collegial relations.

I think that today, three years later, I'm already more a teacher than a builder. Quite definitely, because when I look at what I say, and how I speak, and how I teach these students. (Riina, 50)

Mostly, after the initial acclimatisation, vocational teachers started to seek cooperation with colleagues and other practitioners considering this as a source of learning and enriching their practice.

I have other people from the same field from different schools, we have a workgroup, we come together we can be competitors...but at the same time when we call each other, ask for materials, ask how you do this? Can you come to my lesson? Then we have support. (Rita, 54)

Positive feedback and organisational support tended to increase the teachers' sense of well-being, organisational identity and in turn, shaped the platform for active professional development and further boundary crossing, which involved the new occupational practice.

Vocational teachers who were characterised by intrinsic motivation and/or who had organisational or workgroup support recognised profound changes in their behaviour and attitudes. Those who focused mainly on the students and the subject, but at the same time had a lack of contact with colleagues within the VET school community, identified themselves as practitioners. Despite some vocational teachers recognising a stronger connection with their occupation, and others with the teaching profession, evaluate cooperation with practitioners as a source of professional development.

Understanding the vocational teacher's role and positions

Several senior teachers considered their own paramount goals supporting students' skill development, securing the students' future lives, teach the next occupational generation and to help students in difficult situations. Several narrated cases revealed the altruistic actions of vocational teachers.

However, in talking about future perspectives some senior as well as some of the middle-aged teachers pointed to the question of age. For example, Rita, in a good physical tone woman noted:

I feel that there should be younger people in front of the class, I feel that I am not so attractive anymore. (Rita, 54)

The way how teachers perceive the role and position of vocational teachers is influenced by former career. For example, for those who have enjoyed considerable autonomy at previous work, the circumstances of vocational teachers were perceived as rather restricted.

The first difference is that vocational teacher is nobody in reality. You are nobody, absolutely. Everything has been decided for you. (Priit, 53)

Future perspectives

While discussing VET teachers' future perspectives, half of the participants plan to work as VET teacher until their retirement. The senior teachers see their future as connected to the same vocational school and subject field where they feel safe. Some of the middle-aged vocational teachers want to create their own businesses.

Eventually, I want to be that kind of guy, who most of the time does things in his own enterprise for people and goes to vocational school to teach ... in my opinion, that would be the best possible solution. (Aivar, 45)

Among middle-aged or younger teachers, some have thought about resigning from vocational teaching because of the lack of autonomy, lack of time, and funding policy. Teachers' contribution to advertising the school and attracting potential students is perceived as time-consuming obligation, which does not coincide with VET teachers' professional work.

I feel almost like a sales secretary or some kind of salesperson. I have to do this and that, to attract students to come to school (Marika, 48)

The younger vocational teachers, who felt that a job in a specific school enabled flexible schedules, professional training, time for family and friends, hobbies and social activities, were satisfied with their careers and were not planning any career changes. Some were planning to get on and dreamt of a future in an organisation which offers wider future perspectives in their specific fields.

... I'd make my choice according to the self-development opportunities in one place or another... a vocational teacher in the IT field you need to be, you need to know everything, you need to belong everywhere, you cannot run in one specific direction, I would like to know more about administrating (Janno, 24)

The motives for further development vary among vocational teachers depending on meanings, they attributed to the vocational teaching (to earn money, opportunity for self-development, sharing their skills, helping others, a dream job).

In conclusion, the future career perspectives of vocational teachers are related to their age, their previous career path, and whether they are oriented more towards their occupational or pedagogical identity. Senior VET teachers consider further work as vocational teachers a familiar and safe career path. Some want to open their own business and pursue a career in their own subject field. Mostly, these are younger or middle-aged teachers who possess significant skills in a specific field.

7 Discussion and conclusion

The results highlighted patterns in terms of how and why the respondents chose the career of a vocational teacher. Becoming a vocational teacher was driven by the limited opportunity structures, including limited suitable options in the local labour market, the need to leave unemployment, seeking self-development possibilities and striving toward their own adolescent calling. In most cases, becoming a vocational teacher was a consequence of rather accidental circumstances, such as responding to an offer from a local vocational school. This trend has also been highlighted by Berger and D'Ascoli (2012). The teachers did not very often exhibit their own agency in choosing a career as a vocational teacher.

At the beginning of their careers as VET teachers, boundary crossing manifested itself in learning and understanding of the organisational culture of a vocational school, changing their behaviour patterns and language style, as well as acquiring pedagogical skills and competencies. Later, after adapting to life as a teacher, to maintain a connection with their occupational field, teachers had to cross boundaries again to retain relationships with enterprises and in their own specialist field. The collaboration with colleagues within their vocational school and those of others, as well as representatives of enterprises and sector organisations, are among the most important factors of successful boundary crossing. However, it turned out that the support from the organization was rather low. Moreover, some VET teachers experienced isolation and frustration, as mentorship was actually not offered.

Becoming a vocational teacher was rarely the first choice on their career path. In the "normal" way, the primary process of socialisation into the world of work took place in an occupational field/culture. Therefore, many vocational teachers see their occupational field as more meaningful and visible and have maintained their vocational or professional identity. However, in some cases, teachers crossed the boundary from being a specialist to a VET teacher, and developed a new hybrid identity (Farnsworth and Higham, 2012) and considered themselves simultaneously a specialist and a teacher.

When looking at the teachers' motives to work, the caring motive is a recurring theme. This harmonises with Köpsén (2014), who associated it with teachers' vocational identity. In our study, the senior teachers expressed the allegiance to their former speciality and at the same time, appreciate that they can teach the next occupational generation. The successful boundary-crossing between communities enables sustainability, as the previous life career still has the meaning because of relations and professional skills. Thus, a sustainable career manifests itself in the social relations in and beyond the VET school and in the sense of self-efficacy provided by educating the next generation of vocational professionals. Moreover, feelings like success

or satisfaction may help VET teachers to overcome the regret of giving up their previous vocational work, as pointed by Sarastuen (2020).

Our study highlighted the dilemma between the two sides – professional working life and working as vocational teachers – vocational/professional and pedagogical. This study revealed that limited collaboration within the occupational or pedagogical community puts the sustainable development of vocational teachers at risk.

At the beginning of their career as a VET teacher, the socialisation into the pedagogical community of the vocational school means boundary crossing in several senses. This finding is supported by Akkerman and Bakker (2011), who highlighted that this process involves a change in professional identification as well as living in to a new cultural environment. Successful socialisation, however, means that to some extent, their identity as a specialist continues to be important.

Our findings confirm that there are some similarities between the careers of VET teachers in Nordic countries. In Sweden (Fejes and Köpsén, 2014) and Finland (Vähäsantanen, Saarinen, Eteläpelto, 2009), some vocational teachers, also use their free time to run their own small businesses and appreciate working in their “own” vocational or professional field. Keeping close contacts with the work in a specialist field is one manifestation of the boundary crossing that occurs between their private life, professional field and vocational teaching. As in Finland, the continuous need among Estonian teachers to cross boundaries between various fields depends foremost on the teacher’s individual efforts, and maintaining this practice would benefit from the support of their vocational school (Vähäsantanen, Saarinen, Eteläpelto, 2009). However, the results suggest that becoming a vocational teacher is a process where the outcome depends on the individual’s own activity and organizational support. This harmonises with a sustainable career perspective, and supporting the existing workforce strengthens the VET organisation and makes it more attractive to the potential VET teachers.

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